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**‘A Thematic Analysis of Digital Marketing and Ethical Practices Among
Online Gurus and Social Media Influencers in the Entrepreneurship
Industry’**

MBA Advanced Entry

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Signed Statements

DECLARATION

This work is being submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of MBA and has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree.

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STATEMENT 1

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Other sources are acknowledged by footnotes giving explicit references. A bibliography is appended.

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Student Name

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I acknowledge that the above-named student has regularly attended the planned meetings and actively engaged in the dissertation supervision process. They have provided regular timely draft chapters of the dissertation and followed given guidance.

Signed

Date

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Abstract

The proliferation of digital marketing has magnified the ethical responsibilities of social media influencers (SMIs). This dissertation examines the marketing strategies of prominent SMIs—Grant Cardone, Tai Lopez, and Dan Lok—to understand how they navigate ethical considerations in their content. The study specifically explores the themes of 'Superficial Value', 'Exploitative Practices', and 'Manipulative Tactics' to discern the impact on consumer perception and behaviour, filling a gap in existing research on digital ethics and influencer impact.

Adopting a constructivist philosophy and an inductive qualitative approach, the study performed a thematic analysis on the Instagram content of the selected influencers during February 2024. The analysis was supplemented by quantitative engagement data, such as likes and engagement rates, to contextualise the findings within broader audience reception patterns. The content was coded for themes that reflect ethical challenges in digital marketing, providing a rich, nuanced picture of current practices.

The most prominent theme, 'Superficial Value', dominated the content, indicating a strong focus on aesthetics and lifestyle aspirations. 'Exploitative Practices' and 'Manipulative Tactics' were less prevalent but highlighted potential ethical issues, such as the exploitation of audience vulnerabilities. Despite these concerns, no guideline violations were detected, suggesting a complex relationship between influencer strategy and platform policy adherence.

The findings confirm the dominance of 'Superficial Value' in influencer content and suggest a sophisticated grasp of ethical boundaries by SMIs, who push persuasive marketing to its limits without overtly breaching platform regulations. This study contributes to the discourse on digital marketing ethics, emphasising the need for enhanced consumer protection and digital literacy. It advocates for more robust regulatory frameworks to address the nuances of digital influence and for continued research to keep pace with the rapid evolution of social media marketing.

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Glossary of Terms

- **Online Gurus:** Individuals who establish themselves as experts or authorities in specific fields through digital platforms. They often use social media, blogs, and websites to disseminate knowledge, offer advice, or sell products and services related to their expertise.
- **Social Media Influencers (SMIs):** People who have gained a significant following on social media platforms. They influence their audience's opinions, behaviours, and purchase decisions, often through content creation that includes endorsements, product placements, and personal narratives.
- **Digital Transformation:** The integration of digital technology into all areas of business and life, fundamentally changing how operations are conducted and value is delivered.
- **Democratisation of Information:** A process where access to information becomes more accessible and widespread, often facilitated by digital technology, leading to a reduction in barriers to accessing knowledge.
- **Information Overload:** A state where the amount of information available exceeds an individual's ability to process it, often leading to overwhelm or difficulty in making decisions.
- **Content Credibility:** The degree to which content is perceived as trustworthy, accurate, and reliable by its audience.
- **Veblenian Entrepreneurship:** A term referring to a form of entrepreneurship that prioritises status and conspicuous consumption over genuine innovation and value creation. Named after economist Thorstein Veblen.
- **Sense-Breaking:** A process in marketing and recruitment where existing beliefs and perceptions are challenged or deconstructed to create openness to new ideas.
- **Sense-Making:** The process of providing a new narrative or framework to understand and internalise new concepts, especially after old beliefs have been challenged.
- **Monetisation Strategies:** Methods employed to generate revenue from content or services, including advertisements, sponsorships, and direct sales of products or courses.
- **Engagement Data:** The metrics that capture how users interact with content on digital platforms
- **Likes:** User indication of approval or enjoyment of content on social media platforms
- **Reels:** Short, engaging video clip used typically on Instagram

Chapter 1: Introduction

The rise of online gurus can be contextualised within technological advancements and the subsequent democratisation of information (Fuchs, 2021) - the concept that ideas, opinions and knowledge, will be accessible anywhere at anytime to everyone. In recent years, the internet and digital technologies have drastically reduced barriers to entry, enabling individuals to share their perceived expertise and knowledge with a global audience. Social media platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, and X play a pivotal role in this phenomenon (Van Dijck, 2013), providing individuals with powerful tools to disseminate content, build personal brands, and engage with audiences on a global scale.

YouTube, for instance, has become a platform with over 2.7 billion people accessing it at least once a month as of 2023, demonstrating its widespread reach and influence (Sprout Social, 2023). The platform's premium service, YouTube Premium, has seen significant growth in subscribers, reaching 80 million in 2022, up from just 1.5 million in 2015, indicating a strong user engagement and a willingness to purchase the platform's content. Moreover, YouTube's user base shows a diverse demographic, with a nearly even split between male and female users and a substantial portion of the audience being young adults aged between 18-24 (Thynx Labs, 2023). This is particularly notable given that most users visit YouTube daily, and around 70% of views come from mobile devices, reflecting the platform's robust mobile presence and its adaptability to user preferences (Thynx Labs, 2023). Additionally, the platform's content consumption trends reveal that YouTube's viewership exceeds that of other major platforms and traditional media, with over 1 billion hours watched globally each day, further underscoring its significance in the realm of digital influence (Sprout Social, 2023).

One of the key drivers behind the proliferation of online gurus is the entrepreneurial culture fostered by the internet (Drucker, 2014). This culture encourages individuals to transform their skills and knowledge into viable business opportunities. This dissertation aims to critically evaluate the ethical dimensions of this entrepreneurial spirit. Central to the study is the democratisation of information. As the internet facilitates easy access to knowledge, online gurus position themselves as experts in specific niches (Castells, 2010). This dissertation seeks to uncover the ethical considerations surrounding the use of information in this context, examining issues related to credibility, accuracy, and transparency. Moreover, the perceived trust and authenticity cultivated by online gurus become focal

points of investigation. This dissertation will critically appraise the ethical dimensions of how online gurus build trust via their content, personal narratives, and engagement with their audience.

In light of this dissertation's focus on ethical practices, the exploration will extend to the monetisation strategies employed by online gurus. This includes scrutinising the ethical considerations surrounding the sale of courses, coaching services, and products related to their expertise (Baggini, 2003). The study will assess whether ethical boundaries are maintained in the pursuit of financial gain. Furthermore, an essential aspect warranting consideration is the regulation of social media platforms. In recent years, there has been increasing scrutiny from governments and regulatory bodies worldwide concerning the role and responsibilities of social media platforms in content moderation, data privacy, and misinformation (Gillespie, 2020). This evolving regulatory landscape has significant implications for online gurus and influencers, especially regarding content creation, user engagement, and advertising practices. This dissertation will explore how these regulations impact the ethical decision-making processes of online gurus/influencers, and how they adapt their strategies in response to legal and societal pressures.

While the overview above provides a foundation for understanding the rise of online gurus, this dissertation will adopt case study approach to offer a nuanced analysis of specific instances within the information, self help and entrepreneurship industry. By examining real-world examples this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the ethical considerations associated with the practices of online gurus and influencers, shedding light on the complexities of their roles in the contemporary digital landscape.

Research Question

What are the ethical implications of the marketing practices employed by online gurus and SMIs in the digital age?

Aims

- To critically explore and analyse the ethical dimensions of the marketing practices of online gurus/SMIs with a focus on credibility, transparency, and consumer impact in the digital landscape.

Objectives

- **Examine the Marketing Tactics:** Investigate and categorise the various marketing strategies employed by online gurus/SMIs, analysing their ethical implications.
- **Study Regulatory Influence:** Review the regulatory landscape and public discourse of influence on the ethical practices of online gurus/SMIs.
- **Recommendations and Best Practices:** Formulate recommendations for ethical best practices for online influencers and/or social media platforms, based on the findings of the research.

Methodology Overview

This dissertation adopts a qualitative research methodology, focusing on case studies. This approach is chosen to facilitate a nuanced exploration of the complex ethical dynamics within the practices of online gurus and influencers in the information, self-help, and entrepreneurship industry.

Selection of Case Studies

Case studies will be carefully selected based on a set of criteria designed to ensure a comprehensive analysis. These criteria include the online presence and influence of the subject, the diversity of their marketing strategies, the extent of public controversy or criticism they have faced, and the variety in their business models. The aim is to include a range of influencers that exemplify different aspects of the ethical challenges in this industry.

The choice of Grant Cardone, Tai Lopez, and Dan Lok as focal subjects of this study is predicated upon their pronounced influence within the digital marketing sphere, the diversity in their approaches, and their behaviour in relation to ethical considerations within their content dissemination practices. This makes them exemplary case studies for scrutinising the ethical dilemmas confronting digital influencers today. Their broad-based appeal and influence advocate for a generalised examination of ethical issues within digital marketing.

Data Collection

Data will be collected from a variety of sources to ensure a multi-dimensional perspective:

- **Publicly Available Content:** Analysis of the influencers' digital content including social media posts, videos, and promotional materials.

- **Consumer Feedback:** Where applicable, examination of customer reviews, testimonials, and feedback on various platforms.
- **Academic and Industry Literature:** Review of existing research and publications on digital marketing ethics, influencer impact, and consumer behaviour.
- **Regulatory and Legal Documents:** Where applicable, scrutiny of any legal or regulatory proceedings involving the case study subjects.

Data Analysis

The collected data will be analysed using thematic analysis, a method that allows for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data. This approach is particularly suitable for qualitative research, where the aim is to interpret various aspects of the research topic.

Ethical Considerations

Given the focus on ethical practices, the research methodology itself will adhere to high ethical standards. This includes respecting the privacy and intellectual property rights of the individuals and content being analysed. Care will be taken to ensure that the analysis and conclusions are presented in a fair, unbiased, and respectful manner.

Limitations

The study will acknowledge its limitations, which include the subjective nature of qualitative analysis, the potential bias in publicly available information, and the limitations inherent in not being able to directly interview the subjects of the case studies.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The digital era has revolutionised how information is crafted, shared, and absorbed, introducing a new cadre of influencers: online gurus and social media influencers (SMIs). This critique delves into the ethical quandaries presented by their digital-age practices. Fuchs (2021) marked the beginning of this discourse with the 'democratisation of information', which also brought about challenges like information overload and content credibility issues. Van Dijck (2013) further explores the role of social media platforms as active shapers of content and public opinion, placing significant ethical responsibilities on both the platforms and the influencers.

The dialogue extends to the ethical intricacies of digital marketing strategies. Baggini (2003) and Gillespie (2020) debate the ethical boundaries of evolving monetisation strategies. Adding depth, Hartmann, Krabbe, and Spicer (2020) discuss Veblenian Entrepreneurship, emphasising the ethical implications of prioritising status and wealth. Schønning et al. (2020) and Liu and Zheng (2024) enrich this conversation by scrutinising the nuanced dynamics of influencer marketing, underscoring the ethical considerations of persuasive strategies and the impact of parasocial relationships. This review aspires to highlight the complex ethical dimensions faced by online gurus and SMIs, underlining the critical need for continued research in the dynamic fields of digital marketing, content creation, and the regulatory frameworks that aim to navigate these challenges.

Digital Transformation and Information Democratisation

The digital era has significantly democratised information, fundamentally altering how knowledge is accessed, shared, and utilised. Fuchs (2021) underscores this transformation, highlighting how the internet has lowered barriers to entry for content creation and distribution, enabling a broader range of individuals, including online gurus and influencers, to share their perceived expertise and insights with a global audience. This shift towards information democratisation has led to a more level playing field, allowing voices from diverse backgrounds to be heard. However, it also introduces challenges such as information overload, making it difficult for consumers to sift through and identify credible content amidst a sea of misinformation.

Lee et al. (2021) delve into the motivations behind consumer engagement with social media influencers (SMIs), shedding light on the socio-psychological factors driving audience interaction in the digital age. Their findings suggest that authenticity,

consumerism, creative inspiration, and envy play significant roles in why consumers choose to follow SMIs across platforms like Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok. This reflects a broader change in consumer behaviour, transitioning from passive reception of information to active seeking of content that resonates with personal interests, values, and goals. The trust that consumers place in digital influencers is thus intricately linked to the influencers' perceived authenticity and credibility.

Fuchs's and Lee et al.'s analyses collectively point to a crucial aspect of the digital transformation: the need for a balance between the benefits of accessible information and the challenges it presents, particularly in terms of information quality and establishing trust. They go on to suggest that as influencers continue to shape consumer attitudes and behaviours, the importance of ethical considerations in content creation and dissemination becomes increasingly evident. This evolution in the digital landscape underscores the need for consumers to develop critical media literacy skills, enabling them to navigate the complex and content-rich online world effectively. This transition towards a democratised but complex information landscape sets the stage for examining the role of social media platforms, which not only facilitate but also shape the creation and dissemination of content. The next section explores how these platforms amplify the reach and influence of online gurus, further complicating the ethical responsibilities of both influencers and platforms.

The Role of Social Media Platforms

In the contemporary digital age, the role of social media platforms has transcended mere content hosting, evolving into a formidable force that shapes public opinion and molds the content dissemination landscape. Van Dijck (2013) initially highlighted this transformation, illustrating how platforms like YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok have become integral in the content creation and dissemination process. Through sophisticated algorithms and user interface designs, these platforms exert considerable influence over which content gains visibility and which voices are amplified, thereby playing a pivotal role in the success and reach of online gurus and social media influencers (SMIs).

This significant influence, however, is accompanied by a spectrum of ethical responsibilities that these platforms must navigate. Goanta and Ranchordás (2020) explore the myriad challenges these platforms face, particularly emphasising the need for a delicate balance between their inherently open nature and the crucial imperative to

shield users from misinformation and unethical practices. They advocate for the implementation of comprehensive systems aimed at mitigating the proliferation of false information while ensuring that promotional content adheres to principles of transparency and ethical integrity. Furthermore, the responsibility for ethical content creation and dissemination extends beyond the platforms to encompass the influencers themselves. Influencers are tasked with navigating the complex ethical landscape of their content production, which includes maintaining transparency about sponsorships, avoiding the endorsement of harmful products, and upholding authenticity in their online persona. This dynamic interplay between the power of social media platforms to influence public discourse and the ethical considerations intrinsic to this influence lays bare the complexities inherent in the digital content landscape.

The contributions of Van Dijck (2013) and Goanta and Ranchordás (2020) underscore the necessity for an intricate balance in managing content ethically and responsibly. They highlight the evolving roles and obligations of social media platforms and influencers in sculpting the digital society, drawing attention to the nuanced ethical and entrepreneurial challenges influencers confront. As these influencers traverse the commercial and ethical terrains of digital entrepreneurship, their strategies for engagement, monetisation, and content curation are of paramount importance. This dialogue sets a foundation for further exploration into how influencers adapt to and influence the ever-changing digital environment, particularly in regard to navigating ethical considerations in their quest for success and impact.

Entrepreneurship Industry and Ethical Implications

In the rapidly evolving digital landscape, the entrepreneurship industry faces a unique set of challenges and opportunities that significantly alter traditional business paradigms. Drucker (2014) provides foundational insights into this shift, emphasising the transformative impact of the internet on entrepreneurial culture. This transformation has facilitated the rise of a new class of entrepreneurs, including online gurus who adeptly utilise digital platforms to amplify their brands and businesses, reaching audiences previously unimaginable.

Building upon Drucker's observations, Hartmann, Krabbe, and Spicer (2020) delve deeper into the nuanced dynamics of modern entrepreneurship through the lens of "Veblenian Entrepreneurship." This concept critically examines the industry's current state, where the

pursuit of status and wealth often overshadows genuine innovation and value creation. Veblenian Entrepreneurship, characterised by the flaunting of luxury and high-status symbols, introduces significant ethical considerations about the authenticity and tangible value of what online gurus offer. This emphasis on external appearances and social standing fosters a culture that can mislead consumers with unrealistic expectations and potentially harmful business practices, veering away from substantial contributions and genuine innovation.

The ethical implications of such entrepreneurship extend to the monetisation strategies employed by digital influencers and gurus. Philosophical and ethical scrutiny by thinkers like Baggini (2003) juxtaposed with Gillespie's (2020) analysis of the evolving regulatory framework, underscore the moral dilemmas and regulatory challenges posed by online content creation and monetisation. This intersection highlights the ethical quandaries involved in maintaining a facade of success and status, pushing online entrepreneurs towards practices that may compromise ethical standards for financial gain.

As digital entrepreneurs navigate this complex landscape, the importance of ethical integrity in their business practices comes to the fore. The discussion on Veblenian Entrepreneurship and its critique not only raises questions about the long-term sustainability of such business models but also emphasises the need for a balanced approach that aligns financial aspirations with ethical practices and genuine value creation. This examination sets the stage for exploring the ethical and regulatory considerations in social media marketing, where authenticity, consumer trust, and ethical monetisation strategies become critical in influencing consumer behaviour and shaping public discourse in the digital age.

Social Media Marketing Ethics

In the evolving landscape of digital marketing, the study of social media influencers (SMIs) and their impact on consumer behaviour has gained paramount importance. Liu and Zheng (2024) delve into the persuasive mechanisms employed by influencers, highlighting the pivotal role of parasocial relationships (PSRs) in enhancing the efficacy of influencer marketing. Their research elucidates how SMIs leverage these one-sided relationships, creating an illusion of intimacy and friendship that significantly influences consumer attitudes and behaviours, including purchase intentions. By employing both deductive and latent thematic analysis approaches, Liu and Zheng not only structure their investigation around well-established themes but also uncover the nuanced dynamics of influencer-

follower interactions. This methodology reveals the complexity of manipulative tactics, the allure of superficial value, and the ethical quandaries posed by exploitative practices and guideline violations within the realm of social media.

Complementing this perspective, Schønning et al. (2020) focus on the ethical implications of these influencer marketing strategies. Their study critically examines how SMIs navigate the fine line between persuasive marketing and manipulative practices, shedding light on the often blurred boundaries of ethical conduct in digital spaces. Schønning underscores the necessity for clearer regulations and guidelines to safeguard both consumers and the integrity of digital marketing practices.

Both Liu and Zheng (2024) and Schønning et al. (2020) contribute significantly to the discourse on digital marketing ethics, emphasising the urgent need for transparency, authenticity, and ethical responsibility in influencer marketing. Together, these studies provide a comprehensive overview of the challenges and opportunities presented by the rise of social media influencers, offering valuable insights for academics, marketers, and policymakers alike. Through their exploration of PSRs, manipulative tactics, and ethical considerations, they highlight the critical balance between influence and integrity in the digital age.

Monetisation Strategies and Regulatory Scrutiny

In the digital marketing arena, the monetisation strategies employed by content creators and the regulatory scrutiny these practices attract represent a complex and evolving field. Baggini (2003) and Gillespie (2020) offer critical insights into this domain, with Baggini exploring the ethical dimensions of monetisation in the digital space. He prompts a reflection on the moral obligations of content creators who navigate the delicate balance between generating profit and maintaining integrity in their content. Gillespie complements this discussion by examining the regulatory challenges that arise as digital technologies and marketing tactics rapidly evolve. He emphasises the need for clear regulatory frameworks to ensure ethical transparency and prevent deceptive practices, highlighting the growing influence of online platforms on public opinion and consumer behavior. The discourse around monetisation and regulation underscores the ethical dilemmas faced by digital marketers in distinguishing between authentic content and commercial endorsements. This necessitates a robust regulatory environment that not only protects consumer privacy and data but also ensures that advertising is transparently differentiated

from regular content. Goanta and Ranchordás (2020) further elaborate on the importance of establishing effective regulations tailored to the unique dynamics of the digital marketing landscape, addressing the critical role of online platforms in overseeing the content disseminated by influencers and content creators.

As the digital landscape continues to morph, the integration of perspectives from Baggini, Gillespie, and Goanta and Ranchordás sheds light on the imperative for content creators and platforms to adhere to ethical standards and regulatory requirements. This approach aims to safeguard consumer interests while fostering an environment of honesty, transparency, and innovation. The ongoing dialogue on monetisation strategies and regulatory scrutiny reveals the necessity for adaptive and forward-thinking regulatory policies that harmonise the pursuit of profit with the ethical responsibilities inherent in digital content creation. As this section transitions into a discussion on the nuanced targeting strategies of recruitment and online course marketing, it becomes evident that the ethical and regulatory considerations in monetisation practices are pivotal in shaping the broader landscape of digital entrepreneurship and influencer marketing.

Targeting Strategies and Online Course Marketing

Michael G. Pratt's examination of identity management within multi-level marketing (MLM) organisations, specifically in "The Good, the Bad, and the Ambivalent: Managing Identification among Amway Distributors" (Administrative Science Quarterly, 2000), offers critical insights into the tactics used by online gurus and mentors. Pratt's study on the sense-breaking and sense-making processes employed in MLM recruitment mirrors the strategies of digital entrepreneurs who target vulnerable or seeking individuals, promising them pathways to success, wealth, or well-being through online courses. This approach often involves challenging existing beliefs (sense-breaking) and introducing new paradigms (sense-making), akin to the transformation promised by online gurus. This methodology resonates with the concept of "Veblenian Entrepreneurship," as discussed by Hartmann, Krabbe, and Spicer (2020), which highlights the enticement of status and wealth in entrepreneurship. Online gurus capitalise on this by offering courses as gateways to success, appealing to the desires and vulnerabilities of their audience.

However, such strategies raise ethical concerns about exploiting these vulnerabilities and the genuine value provided by these courses. The importance of ethical marketing and the avoidance of manipulative tactics are emphasised, along with the need for creating

supportive community spaces rather than reinforcing unrealistic expectations. Moreover, the regulatory landscape discussed by Gillespie (2020) highlights the need for transparency and honesty in digital marketing, especially when engaging with susceptible audiences. The comparison to MLM strategies underscores the necessity for stringent ethical and regulatory standards to protect consumers in the digital course market. In wrapping up, the synthesis of Pratt's analysis with the findings of Hartmann, Krabbe, and Spicer uncovers a sophisticated landscape of digital marketing strategies targeting vulnerable demographics. It stresses the significance of adhering to ethical practices and the imperative for regulatory oversight to safeguard consumer interests in the digital domain. Understanding these dynamics is essential for responsibly navigating the complex world of digital marketing, ensuring that the pursuit of success does not overshadow the ethical responsibilities owed to consumers.

Literature Review Summary

This review critically evaluates the ethical challenges faced by online gurus against the backdrop of the digital landscape's evolution. Fuchs (2021) highlights the double-edged sword of information democratisation, facilitating widespread knowledge access while complicating content credibility. Social media's role, as discussed by Van Dijck (2013), further complicates this by influencing content dissemination and consumer behaviour, with Lee et al. (2021) providing insights into consumer motivations. The responsibility of content management on these platforms is underscored by Gillespie (2020) and Goanta and Ranchordás (2020), emphasising the ethical onus on both platforms and influencers. Schønning et al. (2020) and Liu and Zheng (2024) delve into the nuanced dynamics of influencer marketing, examining the ethical boundaries of persuasive tactics and the impact of parasocial relationships. Pratt's exploration of sense-breaking and sense-making processes, alongside Hartmann, Krabbe, and Spicer's (2020) critique of Veblenian Entrepreneurship, illustrates how gurus often exploit vulnerabilities, prioritising status over substantive contributions. This, coupled with Baggini's (2003) reflection on monetisation ethics, highlights the moral imperatives for transparency and integrity in digital content creation. This synthesis of digital transformation, entrepreneurial ethics, and regulatory scrutiny encapsulates the intricate ethical landscape navigated by influencers, underscoring the critical balance between influence and ethical responsibility in the digital age.

Chapter 3: Methods

The evolution of digital marketing has introduced complex ethical challenges, necessitating a nuanced approach to research. This study adopts a comprehensive methodology grounded in constructivist philosophy and primarily qualitative research approaches, aiming to explore the ethical practices of digital influencers. The methodology is designed to capture the multifaceted nature of digital marketing ethics, drawing on established research traditions to ensure a rigorous and insightful investigation.

Research Philosophies

This study is grounded in a constructivist research philosophy, which acknowledges that knowledge, including ethical standards, is shaped through social processes and personal experiences (Creswell, 2018). By applying this philosophy to the digital marketing ethics context, the research acknowledges the fluidity of consumer perceptions and the subjective nature of ethical judgment. It is recognised that these perceptions are influenced by cultural and personal values and the changing dynamics of digital platforms (Bryman, 2016). The constructivist stance facilitates an exploration of how digital marketing ethics are understood and enacted, thus contributing to the discourse on ethical practices in online spaces (Kozinets, 2015).

Approaches to Research

Adhering to an inductive research approach, this study focuses on collecting qualitative data from various sources related to digital influencers, with the aim of developing theories concerning ethical practices and transparency in digital marketing (Thomas, 2011). This approach allows the research to remain open to new insights and patterns that emerge from the data, facilitating the discovery of underlying principles that govern ethical marketing practices. Creswell (2018) highlights the suitability of this approach for exploratory research, where the goal is to understand complex phenomena without the constraints of predefined hypotheses. By analysing the behaviours, strategies, and content of influencers like Cardone, Lopez, and Lok, the study seeks to uncover the nuanced ways in which they navigate ethical considerations, leveraging the inductive approach to build a grounded understanding of the ethical considerations and practices in the digital marketing landscape.

Research Strategies

A case study strategy was chosen in order to achieve an in-depth understanding of the ethical considerations in digital marketing. Yin (2009) advocates for case studies as a means to explore complex phenomena within their real-life contexts, making it an ideal strategy for examining the nuanced ethical dilemmas faced by digital influencers. It also allows for a detailed examination of the interplay between personal branding, consumer engagement, and ethical considerations. This methodological choice is supported by the work of Thomas (2011), who underscores the value of case studies in social science research for their ability to provide detailed insights into individual cases, offering a lens through which to explore broader patterns and themes in ethical digital marketing practices.

Case Selection

The selection of Grant Cardone, Tai Lopez, and Dan Lok as subjects for this study is predicated on their significant impact and varied strategies within the digital marketing realm. These influencers have been chosen based on criteria such as their vast following, diversity in marketing approaches, and their behaviour in relation to ethical discussions in their content dissemination (Hollensen, 2019). Cardone's aggressive real estate marketing, Lopez's lifestyle and personal success narratives, and Lok's focus on high-ticket sales programs present a wealth of data for examining the ethical dimensions of influence in digital marketing (Eisend, 2019; Cialdini, 2007). Their diverse strategies offer a comprehensive view of the ethical considerations in digital marketing, providing a broad spectrum of practices for analysis. This selection enables the study to cover a range of areas, from transparency to consumer manipulation, offering insights into the complexities of maintaining ethical integrity in the digital space.

Research Choices

Opting for a primarily qualitative approach, the study emphasises the analysis of non-numerical data to uncover the ethical implications and strategies of digital influencers. This choice is grounded in the belief that qualitative research, with its focus on depth and richness of data, is particularly well-suited to exploring complex, multifaceted phenomena like ethics in digital marketing (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). The use of thematic analysis on secondary data (Braun and Clarke, 2006, Krippendorff, 2018) offers a systematic evaluation of the influencers' digital content, including social media content to identify patterns and themes related to ethical considerations.

While the study primarily adopts a qualitative approach to delve into the ethical implications and strategies of digital influencers, it also acknowledges the importance of quantitative data in enriching this analysis (Creswell, 2018). Incorporating quantitative aspects, such as the number of 'likes' or engagement rates, provides a multifaceted view that combines the depth of qualitative insights with the breadth of quantitative measures. This integrated approach allows for a more comprehensive examination of digital influencers' reach and the public's reception to their ethical stances, thereby offering a fuller picture of ethical practices within digital marketing.

Time Horizons

The research employs a cross-sectional design, as recommended by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016), focusing on data collected during the period of February 1-29, 2024. Acknowledging practical time constraints, this specific timeframe allowed for a focused yet thorough exploration of the latest trends, challenges, and ethical considerations in digital marketing, thereby ensuring the research's relevance and timeliness within the rapidly evolving digital landscape. This design allows for a timely and relevant exploration of ethics in the digital marketing domain by examining contemporary examples of influencer marketing.

Techniques and Procedures

Employing thematic analysis techniques, the study will examine the digital content produced by the selected influencers, guided by the methodologies outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006). Deductive and latent approaches were employed within the analysis, allowing for an exploration of the themes at hand. These methods facilitated a nuanced examination of manipulative tactics, superficial value, exploitative practices, and guideline violations among social media influencers.

The significance and relevance of these themes have been corroborated by various academic studies, such as Lee et al. (2021), Goanta and Ranchordás (2020) and Zheng (2024), which provide insightful analysis on the persuasive power of social media influencers, the need for regulation and the critical role of parasocial relationships in influencer marketing. This body of work underscores the complexity of influencer-follower dynamics and the intricate balance between information, entertainment, and authenticity in shaping audience perceptions and behaviours. This approach enables the identification

and interpretation of recurring themes related to ethical considerations, marketing strategies, and their impacts on consumer perceptions.

The chosen platform was Instagram as it is one of the most popular social media sites (Dixon, 2024) with a focus on image and video sharing. Themes were inspired by key findings in existing literature: Lee et al. (2021) highlighted the impact of 'superficial value' in influencer content, Goanta and Ranchordás (2020) discussed the potential for 'exploitative practices' and 'guideline violations' challenges in digital marketing, and Zheng (2024) explored 'manipulative tactics' used by influencers. These works provided a solid foundation for investigating the ethical practices of digital influencers across these themes:

Manipulative Tactics

Strategies employed to influence or control others' behaviour or perceptions deceitfully. These include the use of psychological triggers such as creating a sense of urgency, scarcity, or invoking fear of missing out (FOMO) to prompt immediate action. Manipulative tactics may also involve presenting information in a way that misleads the audience by omission, exaggeration, or distortion of facts. The study looked to identify content that create an artificial deadline for an offer, use countdown timers, or employ language that suggests immediate action is necessary to avoid loss and/or the use of emotionally charged words or phrases intended to elicit specific reactions or decisions from the audience.

Superficial Value

Content that prioritises form over substance, often characterised by lifestyle marketing that emphasises luxury, ease, or aesthetic appeal without providing meaningful insight, value, or engagement. This includes overly curated visuals that may not reflect reality, virtue signalling without substantive action, and content that serves the poster's interests under the guise of providing value to the audience. The study looked to identify content that showcased an extravagant lifestyle or possessions as indicators of success, without offering tangible advice or insights into achieving similar outcomes. This includes the use of buzzwords or concepts that suggest moral superiority or alignment with popular causes without evidence of genuine commitment or impact.

Exploitative Practices

Approaches that leverage the audience's vulnerabilities, aspirations, or insecurities for personal gain. This includes marketing that makes unrealistic promises about success, wealth, health, or happiness, and may involve exploiting personal stories or circumstances to create a false sense of relatability or trust. The study looked to identify content that promised life-changing results with minimal effort, investment, or risk, particularly those targeting individuals seeking quick solutions to complex problems. This includes the use of personal or emotional narratives to establish credibility or trust, especially if followed by a sales pitch or call to action that implies similar success is easily attainable by the audience.

Guideline Violation

Content that operates in grey areas or outright violates established regulatory, legal, or platform-specific policies. This can include deceptive advertising, undisclosed endorsements or partnerships, or content that fails to adhere to ethical standards set forth by regulatory bodies.

The dataset comprised social media posts published via Instagram from the selected case study subjects over the period of February 1-29, 2024. A criterion for inclusion was established to ensure the authenticity and originality of the content - any posts that were not originally created by the study subjects but were reposted from other sources were systematically excluded from the dataset. Additionally, one piece of content within the dataset did not display the total number of likes—a feature that could be due to platform-specific privacy settings or the content creator's choice. Consequently, this post could not be included in the quantitative analysis and was marked as 'N/A' (Not Applicable) in the corresponding 'likes' column of the Numbers spreadsheet. This notation ensures clarity and accuracy in the dataset while acknowledging the occasional limitations imposed by the variability in social media content display settings. This safeguard was put in place to maintain the integrity of the analysis and to ensure that the findings were a true representation of the subjects' own content strategies and their direct impact on user engagement.

Each piece of content was systematically logged into a 'Numbers' spreadsheet, enabling the organisation and subsequent thematic categorisation. The process included a detailed

examination of the posts' captions or an appropriate description of the visuals presented within the content, contingent on which aspect was more relevant for the analysis. A dual categorisation system was employed, capturing both the thematic essence of the posts and the nature of the content as either a static image (post) or a dynamic video (reel). Annotations were made to include both the qualitative essence of the content as well as quantitative data, in terms of an engagement analysis allowed for a data-driven exploration of how different content themes resonate with audiences, evidenced by likes and engagement rates across various social media formats, including reels and posts. This was captured as a snapshot of audience engagement at a specific moment in time. Specifically, the number of 'likes' on each post was recorded to serve as a measure of popularity and engagement, with the understanding that these metrics were accurate as of the data collection cessation date, March 12, 2024.

It is recognised that such metrics are dynamic and subject to change, potentially altering post-analysis. However, for the purpose of this research, they provide a static quantitative benchmark against which the qualitative essence of the content was evaluated. This time-bound data capture enabled a focused analysis of the content strategies employed by the case study subjects, offering insight into the correlation between the content features and user engagement levels at the point of data collection, thus contributing to a deeper understanding of the influencers' approaches to digital marketing ethics and the prevailing ethical narratives within their content at that time.

Ethical Considerations

In utilising secondary data for this study, the research adheres to principles of respect, confidentiality, and integrity, ensuring that the analysis of public materials does not misrepresent the intentions or actions of the subjects (Mertens, 2015). This approach respects the public nature of the data while acknowledging the influencers' rights to privacy and dignity in the interpretation and dissemination of findings. By focusing on publicly available content, the study mitigates ethical risks associated with primary data collection, such as informed consent and potential harm to participants, ensuring that the research remains respectful and ethical in its examination of digital marketing practices. Links to each post is provided in the accompanying spreadsheet, facilitating direct access to the original content. This measure ensures that the research does not infringe on copyright laws or the digital influencers' intellectual property rights, further upholding the standards of respect, confidentiality, and integrity in the dissemination of findings.

Summary

This comprehensive methodology, grounded in constructivist philosophy and employing a qualitative, inductive approach, is designed to explore the complex ethical considerations in digital marketing. Through detailed case studies and thematic analysis, the research aims to offer insights into the ways in which digital influencers navigate the evolving standards of ethical practice in the digital age. By focusing on the rich, qualitative data gleaned from the influencers' digital content, the study seeks to contribute to the broader discourse on ethics in digital marketing, providing a grounded understanding of the challenges and opportunities presented by the digital marketing landscape.

Chapter 4: Research Findings

Overview

The analysis of themes across the content posted by digital influencers Grant Cardone, Tai Lopez, and Dan Lok shows that 'Superficial Value' was the predominant theme, with 104 occurrences (84.55%) out of the total (123) themes identified. 'Exploitative Practices' were noted in 17 instances (13.82%), whereas 'Manipulative Tactics' were the least observed, with just 2 cases (1.63%). No instances of 'Guideline Violation' were recorded (see figures 1 & 2).

	Grant Cardone	Tai Lopez	Dan Lok	Total	% of Total
Manipulative Tactics	2	0	0	2	1.63%
Superficial Value	42	55	7	104	84.55%
Exploitative Practices	4	12	1	17	13.82%
Guideline Violation	0	0	0	0	0.00%
Total	48	67	8	123	

	Grant Cardone	Tai Lopez	Dan Lok	Avg. %
Manipulative Tactics	4.17%	0.00%	0.00%	1.39%
Superficial Value	87.50%	82.08%	87.50%	85.69%
Exploitative Practices	8.33%	17.92%	12.50%	12.92%
Guideline Violation	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Figure 1: Total Number of themes recorded

Figure 2: Engagement Themes as Percentage of Total

Combined Engagement Analysis

Across all individuals (see figure 3), there are 96 REELS with a combined total of 384,558 likes. A total of 27 POSTS accumulated 346,202 likes. Combining REELS and POSTS, there are 730,760 likes overall. REELS hold a majority share with 52.62% of total likes, while POSTS follow with 47.38%. The average likes per REEL and POST are 3,664.37 and 7,764.17 respectively. Likes categorised by themes show 'Superficial Value' with the highest percentage of likes at 89.48%, followed by 'Exploitative Practices' at 9.64%, and 'Manipulative Tactics' at 0.88%. No guideline violations were reported. Superficial Value content garnered the most likes at 653,849, followed by 'Exploitative Practices' with 70,451, and 'Manipulative Tactics' with 6,460.

	Grant Cardone REELS	Grant Cardone POSTS	Tai Lopez REELS	Tai Lopez POSTS	Dan Lok REELS	Dan Lok POSTS	Total REELS	Total POSTS	Combined Totals	% Likes per Theme
Type # REEL or POST	30	18	58	9	8	0	96	27	123	
Manipulative Tactics	1268	5192	0	0	0	0	1268	5192	6460	0.88%
Superficial Value	212571	254084	119188	61243	6763	0	338522	315327	653849	89.48%
Exploitative Practices	7484	13863	36611	11820	673	0	44768	25683	70451	9.64%
Guideline Violation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%
Likes Total	221323	273139	155799	73063	7436	0	384558	346202	730760	
% Total	44.76%	55.24%	68.08%	31.92%	100%	0%	52.62%	47.38%		
Avg. Likes per Type	7377.43	15174.39	2686.19	8118.11	929.50	0.00	3664.37	7764.17		
Avg. Likes	10301.30		3415.90		929.50		4882.23			
Engagement Rate (ER)	0.22%		0.12%		0.05%		0.13%			

Figure 3: Engagement Analysis Summary

Thematic Analysis

Superficial Value

The analysis highlights 'Superficial Value' as the most common theme among the digital influencers. This theme accounts for 87.50% of Grant Cardone's and Dan Lok's content, while Tai Lopez shows a slightly lower percentage at 82.08%. On average, 'Superficial Value' represents an average of 85.69% of the total content themes.

This theme often featured content that emphasised lifestyle elements. For example, Grant Cardone's content under this theme frequently involved portrayals of an aspirational lifestyle, with a focus on aesthetic appeal and perceived value, such as depictions of private jets, helicopters and luxury cars (Cardone, 2024b).

Additionally, Tai Lopez's posts often appeared to employ virtue signalling a practice where one indicates or suggests moral superiority, in combination with lifestyle marketing. In a post, Lopez stated:

“Take a day off from the hustle and grind of modern life. Clear your mind.”

(Lopez, 2024)

Exploitative Practices

'Exploitative Practices' emerge as the second most frequent theme. Tai Lopez's content includes this theme at 17.92%, which is the highest among the three influencers. Dan Lok's content has 12.50% of this theme, and Grant Cardone's content includes it at 8.33%. The average occurrence of 'Exploitative Practices' across all influencers' content is 12.92%.

This theme often utilised personal, emotional and aspirational narratives, such as this post from Cardone:

“Financial freedom has been a game-changer for me and my family. It's not just about the money; it's about the choices and opportunities it provides. When you achieve financial freedom, you're no longer bound by financial constraints, allowing you to design your life on your terms...”

(Cardone, 2024c)

Manipulative Tactics

'Manipulative Tactics' are the least represented theme, with an average occurrence of 1.39% across the influencers. Only Grant Cardone's content includes this theme, at 4.17%, while Tai Lopez and Dan Lok do not have any content categorised under this theme.

Despite the low frequency, when manipulative tactics were employed, they exhibited certain characteristics. These tactics typically included language that created a sense of urgency or scarcity, potentially prompting immediate action from the audience.

For instance, Grant Cardone's usage of manipulative tactics can be evidenced by a particular statement on his social media platform, where he leverages the scarcity of available seats to create a sense of urgency among potential attendees.

"7 years in a row we Sold Out what Forbes Called the #1 Networking Event in the world without ever announcing a speaker [...] This year we are almost sold out with only 60 days left [...] Less than 50 premier seats left".

(Cardone, 2024)

Guideline Violation

None of the influencers' content was categorised under 'Guideline Violation,' with all influencers showing 0% for this theme, indicating no observed violations within the analysed content.

Individual Engagement Analysis

Cardone has 30 REELS with a total of 221,323 likes, making up 44.76% of his total likes. His 18 POSTS received 273,139 likes, contributing to 55.24% of his total likes, which is notable considering there are 25% fewer POSTS than REELS. On average, REELS received 7,377.43 likes each, while POSTS averaged 15,174.39 likes. The engagement rate (ER) for Cardone's content is 0.22%.

Lopez has a more extensive REELS collection, totalling 58, with 155,799 likes (68.08% of his total). He has fewer POSTS, only 9, gathering 73,063 likes, which is 31.92% of his total. REELS have a much lower average like count at 2,686.19, while his POSTS see a higher average at 8,118.11 likes. Lopez's ER is slightly lower than Cardone's at 0.12%.

Dan Lok's engagement is solely from 8 REELS, which have received 7,436 likes, accounting for 100% of his engagement from the data provided. Each REEL averages 929.50 likes. Lok's ER is markedly lower at 0.05%.

Chapter 5: Discussion

Interpretations & Implications

This research reveals a complex picture of the marketing tactics employed by SMIs, with a heavy reliance on lifestyle and aspirational characterised as 'Superficial Value', while this content undeniably captivates audiences and drives digital engagement, its ethical implications and societal impact warrant a careful and nuanced examination. This prevalence of this theme reflects a preference for aesthetic appeal and social status (Cardone, 2024b), a culture critiqued by Hartmann et al. (2020) as 'Veblenian Entrepreneurship' for prioritising appearances over genuine value and innovation, raising ethical questions about the authenticity and long-term impact of such practices.

These concerns also resonate with the potential mental health implications of social media use (Schønning et al., 2020). This emphasis on luxury and success mirrors the broader societal trends towards aspirational content and/or escapism that Schønning et al (2020) highlight as being linked to negative mental health outcomes. This connection underscores the necessity for digital literacy and a balanced portrayal of success in digital narratives to mitigate unrealistic expectations. Both studies illuminate the critical intersection between digital media consumption and mental well-being, advocating for a more nuanced understanding and approach to online content engagement.

While less prevalent, 'Exploitative Practices' also illustrated the potential exploitation of audience aspirations for financial freedom and lifestyle transformation. A notable example was the timing of the "Veteran Wealth Formula" (Cardone, 2024d), a program ostensibly targeting US veterans, a demographic that may be particularly susceptible to promises of financial stability and freedom. This was immediately followed by content (Cardone, 2024c) highlighting the portrayal of an aspirational lifestyle, which could be seen as a strategic amplification effort.

This subsequent content, laden with aspirational themes, could be interpreted as a method to catalyse the impact of the initial announcement, thereby possibly exploiting the heightened emotional state that aspirational content is intended to evoke, serving as a vivid illustration of the potential rewards the "Veteran Wealth Formula". It is this critical timing and thematic reinforcement that can potentially harness an individual's aspirations post-announcement, engendering a stronger compulsion towards the offerings put forth by the influencer. This aligns with the concepts of sense-breaking and sense-making (Pratt,

2000) and reveals how online gurus often target potentially vulnerable or disillusioned individuals, offering transformative narratives that align with the concept of 'Veblenian Entrepreneurship' (Hartmann, Krabbe and Spicer, 2020).

There is also correlation within this theme, illustrated by Tai Lopez's proclamation of "The Ultimate Scam in This World" (Lopez, 2024b) and the subsequent critique of societal pillars such as, therapists, doctors and economists, as having failed the masses. This introduces a stark perspective on conventional wisdom and societal norms. This narrative is echoed in Grant Cardone's assertion that "the middle class are being lied to" (Cardone, 2024e) regarding traditional financial advice, such as buying a house or investing in a 401(k).

Both influencers leverage these statements to question the efficacy and honesty of established practices, positioning their alternative approaches, which are predominantly centred around non-traditional investment avenues, portrayed as superior solutions. By challenging established norms and promoting alternative lifestyles and financial strategies, Lopez and Cardone not only market their own products and services but also potentially exploit the vulnerabilities and disillusionments of their audiences. This echoes the concerns over the credibility of content raised by Fuchs (2021), underscoring the complex ethical responsibilities placed upon influencers by the democratisation of information and the power dynamics of social media platforms (Van Dijck, 2013; Lee et al., 2021).

The theme of 'Manipulative Tactics,' identified as the least represented across the influencers analysed, offers a nuanced perspective on the ethical considerations in digital marketing practices. The utilisation of language that instills a sense of urgency or scarcity, as observed in Cardone's promotions (Cardone, 2024a), underscores a deliberate approach to influence consumer behaviour and decision-making processes. This strategy, while potentially effective in driving immediate action, raises ethical concerns regarding the manipulation of consumer perceptions and choices, potentially leading to decision-making under pressure rather than informed consent.

The absence of guideline violations in the data presents an aspect of digital marketing ethics and regulatory compliance which could be seen in many ways. For example, their perceived ability to navigate the complex landscape of social media regulations suggests a deep understanding and application of compliance strategies. This might indicate that they

are adept at crafting messages that push the boundaries of persuasive marketing without crossing into territory that explicitly violates platform guidelines, which is especially important given Cardone and Lopez utilise social media at a high frequency (Figure 1).

Alternatively, the lack of guideline violations also raises questions about the adequacy and scope of existing regulatory frameworks to address the subtleties of manipulative and exploitative practices. It suggests that current guidelines may not fully encapsulate or address the ethical complexities inherent in digital marketing strategies that leverage psychological tactics.

However, these individuals are not exempt from public scrutiny or legal challenges. Cardone faced a class action lawsuit alleging that his social media posts misled investors regarding the potential profits of his real estate deals. The lawsuit was initially dismissed but later reinstated by an appeals court (Dilakian and Alvarado, 2022), highlighting the controversy surrounding Cardone's business practices. Tai Lopez, known for his Retail Ecommerce Ventures (REV), faced allegations from investors who claimed a loss of \$240 million. They accused Lopez of fraudulent practices in transforming failing retail brands into successful e-commerce ventures. Ventures like Pier 1 Imports and RadioShack struggled under REV's management (Fickenscher, 2023), intensifying investor concerns over Lopez's business strategies.

A detailed review from a participant in Lok's programs suggests that aggressive upselling and high-pressure tactics are used to promote more expensive tiers of mentorship and training can be problematic. This critique acknowledges the skills Lok teaches but questions the ethical implications of his marketing and sales strategies (Kanehara, 2022). Additionally, an interview with a Dan Lok student who regrets his purchase further emphasises the financial and emotional toll that such high-ticket programs can impose on individuals (Coffeezilla, 2019). These critiques of Cardone, Lopez and Lok and their alleged misleading promises, emphasise the ethical dilemmas inherent in monetisation strategies (Baggini, 2003).

Limitations

In conducting this investigation into the digital practices of influencers such as Grant Cardone, Tai Lopez, and Dan Lok, the research was delineated by specific methodological constraints. Primarily, the scope of the study was confined to the month of February 2024,

providing a snapshot rather than a longitudinal analysis of the influencers' activities. This limitation restricts the examination of content themes and engagement patterns, which may fluctuate or evolve over broader timescales. The transient nature of digital influence, characterised by shifting societal trends and the personal evolution of influencers, necessitates a more extended period of observation for a nuanced understanding of these dynamics.

Further, the research was conducted exclusively within the confines of Instagram as the sole platform for data collection. While Instagram offers a rich medium for the conveyance of visual and textual narratives, this platform-centric approach may have constrained the breadth of the investigation. The digital ecosystem is comprised of a diverse array of platforms, each fostering unique cultures, engagement norms, and content strategies. The exclusive focus on Instagram potentially overlooks the multifaceted strategies deployed by influencers across different platforms, such as Twitter's concise textual interactions or YouTube's in-depth video content. The specificity of the platform, therefore, points to the necessity for a multi-platform analytical approach to capture the comprehensive scope of digital influencer strategies.

Additionally, the study encountered a limitation in the quantitative dimension, specifically the inability to ascertain the number of likes for a particular post by Cardone (Cardone, 2024d). This absence introduces a gap in the quantitative dataset. However, it should be noted that this gap would likely be mitigated by the overall volume of data collected. The absence of engagement data from a single post is not expected to significantly alter the outcome of the data analysis or the overarching findings of the research.

Despite these methodological constraints, this research provides valid insights into the ethical implications of digital influencers' practices. The focused analysis within February 2024 on Instagram offers a snapshot prevailing content themes and engagement strategies, reflective of current digital influence dynamics and the volume of data collected compensates for the absence of specific engagement metrics from a single post, ensuring the reliability of the overall findings.

Summary

This research addresses the ethical implications of the marketing and business practices employed by digital influencers in the digital age, with a focus on Grant Cardone, Tai

Lopez, and Dan Lok, three prominent figures whose social media content offers a window into the strategies that underpin their online influence. The analysis uncovered a prevailing theme of 'Superficial Value' across their engagements, a reflection of content that emphasises aesthetic allure and lifestyle aspirations. Alongside, 'Exploitative Practices' and 'Manipulative Tactics' emerge as secondary yet significant themes, underscoring the ethical complexities these influencers navigate. The predominant appeal of 'Superficial Value' content, as evidenced by its substantial engagement rates, highlights the critical intersection of ethical marketing practices and consumer impact, thus situating this research within the broader discourse on the ethical standards and responsibilities of digital influencers.

Chapter 6: Conclusions

This investigation set out to investigate the ethical implications of marketing practices employed by online gurus/SIMs, focusing on the likes of Grant Cardone, Tai Lopez, and Dan Lok. By delving into the essence of their online influence, this research unraveled the predominance of what we've termed 'Superficial Value' within their digital footprint. This phenomenon—characterised by a facade of value overshadowing genuine substance—casts a shadow on the ethical standards maintained by such influencers, spotlighting a complex dance between moral marketing practices and their sway over consumer actions.

The allure of 'Superficial Value' content, evidenced by its significant engagement rates, underscores its formidable effect in shaping consumer preferences and behaviours. This aligns with Hartmann et al.'s (2020) critique on 'Veblenian Entrepreneurship', which posits that the allure of status and aspiration often trumps true innovation. Such revelations not only echo earlier scholarly discussions but also unveil a potential oversight in appreciating the broader societal and psychological repercussions of social media narratives.

Moreover, the identification of 'Exploitative Practices' and 'Manipulative Tactics' as secondary themes further muddies the ethical waters. These strategies reveal a deliberate exploitation of audience vulnerabilities, reminiscent of Pratt's (2000) discussions on the manipulation of perception. The tactics employed by these influencers, aimed at individuals in pursuit of growth, mirror the predatory nature of MLM recruitment strategies, underscoring the critical need for ethical integrity in digital marketing.

Unexpectedly, the lack of overt regulatory infractions in the scrutinised influencer content suggests a shrewd, albeit morally ambiguous, navigation of platform policies. This finding challenges preconceived notions about influencer conduct, hinting at a sophisticated yet ethically questionable exploitation of regulatory frameworks.

In summary, this research highlights the ethical quandaries of digital influence, underscoring an imperative for more rigorous ethical and regulatory oversight to safeguard consumer interests. By casting light on the ethical dilemmas at play, this research marks a step forward in understanding the complexities of interrelations between digital influencers, consumer behaviour, and moral standards. It highlights the further need for investigation into the evolving tactics of digital influencers and their long-lasting impact, advocating for an extensive, longitudinal exploration to fully grasp the intersection of ethical stakes and

the potential for authentic value offered by online figures. This research hopefully contributes insights to the discourse on digital ethics, urging a reevaluation of the frameworks governing social media/digital marketing and influence.

Recommendations

In terms of practical recommendations, the foundation for fostering an ethical digital environment lies in enhancing digital literacy among social media users. This is especially important given the correlation between negative mental health outcomes and increased social media use (Schønning et al., 2020). By implementing programs aimed at developing critical evaluation skills, audiences can be empowered to discern the authenticity and ethical implications of influencer content. As we have increasingly moved from an analog to a digital era, educational institutions are positioned as pivotal architects in sculpting an informed user base. These educational initiatives would not only illuminate the nuances of digital content but also cultivate a discerning eye among audiences, enabling them to navigate the complexities of influencer marketing with informed skepticism.

Parallel to educational endeavours, the establishment of a platform-specific code of practice for influencers and an update of consumer protection laws from the digital era would mark a critical step toward ethical clarity. Drawing inspiration from governing bodies with a rigorous code of practice, such as the Association of British Pharmaceutical Industry (ABPI) (Prescription Medicines Code of Practice Authority, 2021) or the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) (Financial Conduct Authority, 2013). This code could mandate that influencers are clearly identified as promotional, ensuring content on their pages or accounts is viewed as such, improving transparency for visitors. Such clarity demarcates promotional endeavours from organic content, fostering an environment where consumer engagement is predicated on informed choice rather than inadvertent persuasion.

To ensure the adherence to these ethical guidelines would necessitate the creation of a social media governing body as discussed by Gillespie (2020), and Goanta and Ranchordás (2020). This entity would not only enforce the code of practice but also mandate membership for platforms wishing to operate within certain jurisdictions. Armed with the authority to levy fines and or bans against non-compliant platforms and individuals, this governing body would instill a culture of self-policing, ensuring that platforms actively monitor and enforce ethical practices among their influencer communities.

Anticipated objections to these proposals, particularly those citing concerns over free speech and expression, merit thoughtful consideration. However, distinguishing between the right to individual expression and the operational terms of business within social media platforms is crucial. This proposed ethical framework does not seek to curb the creative freedoms of individuals but rather to ensure that promotional activities are conducted with explicit transparency, safeguarding consumer interests without compromising the essence of free expression.

In terms of further research, emphasis should be placed on longitudinal studies, which are paramount for charting the development of influencers' content strategies, audience engagement, and the durability of their educational and mentorship offerings over time. This longitudinal approach is essential for unearthing the intricate dynamics and persistent effects of digital influence. Furthermore, broadening the research to encompass an array of social media platforms is critical. Engaging in a cross-platform analysis will reveal the manner in which influencers tailor their strategies to align with the distinct cultures and user expectations of each platform, thereby illustrating unique ethical considerations and patterns of engagement. Additionally, it became evident that the content published by the participants often did not adhere to the distinct thematic boundaries. This overlapping nature of themes indicates a complex interplay of various strategies and messaging techniques.

Recognising this, future research could benefit from the identification and analysis of sub-themes. Such an approach would allow for a finer dissection of the data, capturing the subtleties and nuances that a broad thematic analysis might overlook. This would enable researchers to gain deeper insights into the multifaceted strategies influencers employ and better understand the nuanced ways in which they engage with and influence their audience. Lastly, evaluating the value provided by influencers' offerings, through a combination of quantitative analysis and qualitative insights gathered from participant feedback, is imperative for identifying discrepancies between the benefits marketed and those actually delivered. This evaluation is vital for fostering transparency and ethical practices within the influencer community.

Word Count

9218 Words

Reference list

- Aw, E.C.-X. and Chuah, S.H.-W. (2021). 'Stop the unattainable ideal for an ordinary me!' fostering parasocial relationships with social media influencers: The role of self-discrepancy. *Journal of Business Research*, 132(7), pp.146–157. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.025>.
- Baggini, J. (2003). *Making sense : philosophy behind the headlines*. Oxford ; New York: Oxford University Press.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006). *Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology*. [online] *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social Research Methods*. 5th ed. [online] N/A. Available at: <https://ktpu.kpi.ua/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/social-research-methods-alan-bryman.pdf>.
- Cardone, G. (2024a). Grant Cardone. [online] Instagram. Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3JEfu8vk3D/>.
- Cardone, G. (2024b). Grant Cardone. [online] Instagram. Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C2zIBt-rpdX/>.
- Cardone, G. (2024c). Grant Cardone. [online] Instagram. Available at: https://www.instagram.com/p/C3AavEcLfx8/?img_index=1.
- Cardone, G. (2024d). Grant Cardone. [online] Instagram . Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C2-G4LWL6IA/>.
- Cardone, G. (2024e). Grant Cardone. [online] Instagram . Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3QLmrlrCn9/>.
- Castells, M. (2010). *The Rise of the Network Society*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Cialdini, R.B. (2007). *Influence: The Psychology of Persuasion*. Collins.
- Coffeezilla (2019). Interviewing a Dan Lok Student - High Ticket Closer Who Regrets His Purchase [SPENT THOUSANDS]. [online] www.youtube.com. Available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GBKlpz_uTMI#:~:text=URL%3A%20https%3A%2F%2Fwww [Accessed 16 Mar. 2024].
- Creswell, J.W. and Poth, C.N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2018). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Dilakian, S. and Alvarado, F. (2022). Appeals Court Reinstates Grant Cardone Class Action Lawsuit. [online] *The Real Deal*. Available at: <https://therealdeal.com/miami/2022/12/28/grant-cardone-is-back-on-the-hook-in-a-class-action-suit/> [Accessed 16 Mar. 2024].

Dixon, S.J. (2024). Most popular social networks worldwide as of January 2024, ranked by number of monthly active users. [online] Statista. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/>.

Drucker, P.F. (2014). *Innovation and Entrepreneurship Practice and Principles*. London: Routledge.

Eisend, M. (2019). Persuasion in Advertising – How to Use Persuasion and Influencing Tools in advertising. *International Journal of Advertising*, 38(1), 4-6.

Fickenscher, L. (2023). Owner of RadioShack, Pier 1 in danger of bankruptcy filing: sources. [online] New York Post. Available at: <https://nypost.com/2023/03/02/owner-of-radioshack-pier-1-in-danger-of-bankruptcy-filing-sources/>.

Financial Conduct Authority (2013). *FCA Handbook - FCA Handbook*. [online] Fca.org.uk. Available at: <https://www.handbook.fca.org.uk/handbook>.

Fuchs, C. (2021). *Social Media: A Critical Introduction*. Los Angeles: Sage.

Gillespie, T. (2020). Content moderation, AI, and the Question of Scale. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), p.205395172094323. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720943234>.

Goanta, C. and Ranchordás, S. (2020). The regulation of social media influencers: an introduction. *The Regulation of Social Media Influencers*, pp.1–20. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788978286.00008>.

Hartmann, R.K., Krabbe, A.D. and Spicer, A. (2020). Towards an Entrepreneurial economy: The Entrepreneurship Industry and the Veblenian Entrepreneur. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 2020(1), p.12819. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5465/ambpp.2020.152>.

Hollensen, S. (2019). *Marketing management : a relationship approach*. 4th ed. Amsterdam: Pearson.

Kanehara, I. (2022). Is Dan Lok a Scam? (My Honest Experience). [online] Ippei Blog. Available at: <https://ippe.com/dan-lok-scam/> [Accessed 16 Mar. 2024].

Kozinets, R.V. (2015). *Netnography : redefined*. Los Angeles Etc.: Sage.

Krippendorff, K. (2018). *Content Analysis : An Introduction to Its Methodology*. 4th ed. Los Angeles, Calif. Etc.: Sage.

Lee, J.A., Sudarshan, S., Sussman, K.L., Bright, L.F. and Eastin, M.S. (2021). Why are consumers following social media influencers on Instagram? Exploration of consumers' motives for following influencers and the role of materialism. *International Journal of Advertising*, 41(1), pp.78–100.

Liu, X. and Zheng, X. (2024). The persuasive power of social media influencers in brand credibility and purchase intention. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02512-1>.

Lopez, T. (2024a). Tai Lopez. [online] Instagram. Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3T293NNxUB/>.

Lopez, T. (2024b). Tai Lopez. [online] Instagram. Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3YGi0Xu3O-/>.

Mertens, D.M. (2015). *Research and evaluation in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods*. Sage.

Pratt, M.G. (2000). The Good, the Bad, and the Ambivalent: Managing Identification among Amway Distributors. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 45(3), p.456. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2667106>.

Prescription Medicines Code of Practice Authority (2021). 2021 Interactive ABPI Code of Practice - Comes into Operation 1 July 2021. [online] www.pmcpa.org.uk. Available at: <https://www.pmcpa.org.uk/the-code/2021-interactive-abpi-code-of-practice/>.

Saima and Khan, M.A. (2020). Effect of Social Media Influencer Marketing on Consumers' Purchase Intention and the Mediating Role of Credibility. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 27(4), pp.1–22. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10496491.2020.1851847>.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2016). *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th ed. Harlow, Essex, England: Pearson Education Limited.

Schønning, V., Hjetland, G.J., Aarø, L.E. and Skogen, J.C. (2020). Social Media Use and Mental Health and Well-Being among Adolescents – a Scoping Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, [online] 11(1949). doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01949>.

Sprout Social (2023). 50+ of the Most Important Social Media Marketing Statistics for 2023. [online] Sprout Social. Available at: <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/social-media-statistics/#youtube-statistics> [Accessed 2024].

Tarleton Gillespie (2021). *CUSTODIANS OF THE INTERNET : platforms, content moderation, and the hidden decisions that shape... social media*. S.L.: Yale University Press.

Thomas, G. (2011). A Typology for the Case Study in Social Science following a Review of Definition, Discourse, and Structure. *Qualitative Inquiry*, [online] 17(6), pp.511–521. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800411409884>.

Thomas, G. and Myers, K. (2015). *The Anatomy of the Case Study*. SAGE.

Thynx Labs. 2023. *YOUTUBE USER STATISTICS 2023*. [online] Available at: <https://thynxlabs.com/youtube-user-statistics/> [Accessed 6 January 2024].

Van Dijck, J. (2013). *The Culture of Connectivity: A Critical History of Social Media*. New York: Oxford University Press, pp.3–23.

Yin, R.K. (2009). Case study research: Design and methods. 4th ed. Los Angeles: Sage Publications.